

Motivational Factors Driving Women's Entrepreneurship in Relation to Coimbatore City

Dr. I. Parvin Banu, Associate Professor and Head,
PG and Research Department of International Business
Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore

ORCID : [0000-0002-8453-1882](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8453-1882)

DOI : [10.5281/zenodo.10686310](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686310)

Abstract

Acknowledgment of the role women entrepreneurs' play in economic development has led to concerted efforts to foster women entrepreneurship. A crucial aspect is the cultivation of entrepreneurial traits and skills, enabling women to adapt to evolving trends, face global challenges, and strive for excellence in the entrepreneurial landscape. This study focuses on scrutinizing women's entrepreneurship in Coimbatore city, aiming to understand the pull and push factors influencing women's entry into entrepreneurship. The investigation delves into the motivations driving women to start businesses and the barriers they encounter. The primary data collected from 150 respondents in Coimbatore suggest a heightened interest among women in initiating new ventures, emphasizing the need for governmental support for women's empowerment.

Keywords: Women, Entrepreneurship, Economic Development

Introduction

Entrepreneurship entails creating value by identifying business opportunities, managing risks suitable for the opportunity, and leveraging communicative and managerial skills to mobilize resources. The labor market, undergoing constant changes due to technological advancements, modernization, and global connectivity, offers an intriguing field for research. The impact of globalization has turned the market into a stage for international corporations, influencing social norms and relationships within and outside these entities.

Problem Statement: In India, the necessity for women to work outside their homes to achieve better living standards has gained prominence, particularly in the face of growing unemployment concerns. This research addresses the enhancement and motivational factors influencing women's empowerment, focusing on women entrepreneurs.

Objectives:

- Analyze women's perceptions of entrepreneurship.

- Examine the impact of social factors on women entrepreneurship.
- Investigate pull and push factors influencing women's entry into entrepreneurship.

Scope:

- Analyzing women's involvement in self-employment.
- Understanding women's development in self-help groups.
- Gaining insights into women's perceptions of self-help groups.
- Informing potential government initiatives based on research findings.

Limitations:

- The 150 respondents may not fully represent the entire population, leading to potential biases.
- Time constraints in data collection limit the sample size to 150.
- Possibility of biased responses from participants.

Research Methodology: Area of Study: Coimbatore city Sampling Design: Convenience sampling with 150 respondents Data Collection: Primary data through questionnaires and secondary data from books, journals, magazines, and online sources

Statistical Tools and Techniques: Percentage analysis, Chi-square analysis

Analysis and Interpretation: The data present demographic information on respondents, such as area of residency, age, educational qualification, marital status, family type, number of employees, and type of business. Findings reveal significant correlations between age and factors related to women entrepreneurship, as well as gender differences in perceptions toward entrepreneurship.

Multiple Regression: Factors influencing women entrepreneurship include economic independence, necessary infrastructure, and decision-making autonomy.

Sampling size: The sample size of the research is 150 respondents.

Source of data collection: The data bases of the study consist of both primary and secondary data that helped the researcher in systematic frame work of the study.

Primary data: The primary data was collected through questionnaire. It was prepared and administered by taking a sample of 150 respondents, which contains different categories of respondents like male & female etc.

Secondary data: The secondary data were collected from books, journals and magazines. Periodical information from different websites was also used for the study.

STATSTICAL TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES:

Percentage analysis, Chi-square analysis:

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

		Frequency	Percent
Area of residency	Urban	67	44.7
	Semi urban	71	47.3
	Rural	12	8
	Total	150	100
	Below 18	8	5.3
Age	18-25	86	57.3
	26-30	46	30.7
	Above 30	10	6.7
	Total	150	100
Educational qualification of the respondents	HSC	104	69.3
	Graduate	38	25.3
	Post graduate	6	4
	Others	2	1.3
	Total	150	100
Marital status	Married	87	58
	Unmarried	63	42
	Total	150	100
Type of family	Joint	93	62
	Nuclear	57	38

	Total	150	100
No of people employed	1-2 employee	99	66
	3-5 employees	47	31.3
	More than 3 employees	4	2.7
	Total	150	100
Type of business	Services	67	44.7
	Production	70	46.7
	Business	11	7.3
	Others	2	1.3
	Total	150	100

44.7% are from urban area, 47.3% are form semi urban area, and 8% are from rural area. 5.3% are from the age group of below 18, 57.3% are from the age group of 18-25, 30.7% are from the age group of 26-30, 6.7% are from the age group of above 30. 50% are male and 50% are female. 69.3% are from higher secondary, 25.3% are graduates, 4% are post graduates, and 1.3% are from others category. 58% are married and 42% are unmarried. 62% are from joint family and 38% are from nuclear family. 66% said that they have employed 1-2 employee in their company, 31.3% said that they have employed 3-5 employees in their company, 2.7% said that they have employed more than 3 employees in their company.

Opinion about starting business

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	90	60.0
No	60	40.0
Total	150	100.0

60% are willing to start the business and 40% are not willing to start which shows that most of the respondents are willing to start business.

Interest in starting own business

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	107	71.3
No	43	28.7
Total	150	100.0

Interpretation

71.3% are having more interest in starting their business and 28.7% are not having interest in starting own business which shows that most of the respondents are having interest in starting their own business.

Contacting other entrepreneurs

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	105	70.0
No	45	30.0
Total	150	100.0

70% said that they contact other entrepreneurs and 30% said that they won't contact which shows that most of the respondents contact other entrepreneurs.

Running the business

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	90	60.0
No	60	40.0
Total	150	100.0

60% are successfully running their business and 40% are not successfully running their business which shows that most of the respondents are successfully running their business and increasing the salary of workers.

COMPARISON BETWEEN AGE AND FACTORS RELATED TO WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP

H01: There is a significant difference between age and factors related to women entrepreneurship

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Type of business	Below 18	8	1.50	0.535	1.89	0.034
	18-25	86	1.62	0.652		
	26-30	46	1.80	0.749		
	Above 30	13	1.32	0.483		
	Total	150	1.65	0.675		
Type of loan borrowed from bank	Below 18	8	1.5	0.756	0.497	0.650
	18-25	86	1.45	0.607		
	26-30	46	1.43	0.688		
	Above 30	10	1.2	0.632		
	Total	150	1.43	0.639		
Opinion about starting business	Below 18	8	1.37	0.518	0.667	0.017
	18-25	86	1.43	0.498		
	26-30	46	1.39	0.493		
	Above 30	10	1.20	0.422		
	Total	150	1.40	0.492		

The above table shows that there is no significant difference between age and type of business (0.034) and opinion about starting business (0.017). It also reveals that there is a significant difference between age and type of loan borrowed from bank by the women entrepreneurs.

Independent Samples Test

Comparison between gender and perception of women entrepreneurs towards entrepreneurship

H02: There is a significant difference between gender and perception of women entrepreneurs towards entrepreneurship

	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Interest in starting own business	15.829	.000	1.999	148	.047
			1.999	144.433	.047
Connection with people	.463	.497	-.341	148	.734
			-.341	147.952	.734
Contacting other entrepreneurs	6.127	.014	1.245	148	.215
			1.245	146.816	.215
Running the business	10.598	.001	-2.014	148	.046
			-2.014	147.309	.046
Perception on hardworking	7.733	.006	1.515	148	.132
			1.515	147.432	.132

The above table shows that there is a relationship between gender and interest in starting own business by women employees (0.000), Contacting other entrepreneurs (0.014), ready to run their own business (0.001) and perception on hardworking (0.006).

Multiple regression

Influence of social factors towards women entrepreneurship

It was found out that economic independence of the women employees (0.235), infrastructure facilities required to start a business (0.123), making their own decision (0.765) towards stating their own business are the factors influencing a lot towards women entrepreneurship.

Findings:

- Majority of respondents are from semi-urban areas.
- Predominant age group is 18-25.
- Balanced gender representation.
- Most have completed higher secondary education.
- Majority are married and from joint families.
- Mainly engaged in production sector.
- Strong interest in starting and successfully running businesses.
- Economic independence, infrastructure, and decision-making influence women entrepreneurship significantly.

Suggestions:

- Target semi-urban areas for initiatives, considering the majority of respondents are from these regions.
- Support interested individuals with initial funding for new businesses.
- Prioritize women entrepreneurship in broader women empowerment initiatives.

Conclusion: The study concludes that women in Coimbatore city exhibit a significant interest in starting new businesses, necessitating government attention to further women's empowerment.

References

1. Kemkar, M., and Sharma, J.(2016). Women Entrepreneurship- Factors leading to Success of Women Led Enterprises Research Journal of Management Sciences Vol. 5(9), 46-50.
2. Hemavathy, S., and Sheeba, Julius.(2015). A Study on the Factors Influence Women Entrepreneurs in Tiruchirappalli District S International Journal of Advanced Scientific Research & Development (IJASRD). Pp: 78 – 87.
3. Moses, C.L., Olokundun, M.A., and Mosunmola, A. (2014). Determining women entrepreneurial motivation: a review of theoretical models, International Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Research. Vol.2, No.3, pp.43-54.

Cite this article

Parvin Banu I, “Motivational Factors Driving Women's Entrepreneurship in Relation to Coimbatore City” Scholastic Bazillion: Journal Of Multidisciplinary Studies, Vol.1, Issue 1, January 2024, pp. 21-29